

User Identification from Time Series of Fitness Data

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Abstract: We explore the threat posed by disclosure of personal fitness information collected by wearable devices. In particular, we study a scenario where an attacker has a list of aggregated records produced by a group of users, which are stored as time series of steps and calories. We introduce a machine learning-based approach to identify one target person in the aggregated data while being in possession of other records from that person. We estimate how accurately an attacker can find the target’s data when aggregated with other users by testing our approach on two public datasets. Our results show that personal fitness data possess identifying capabilities that should be accounted when they are shared or disclosed.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, smart fitness trackers have seen a substantial increase in sales, along with the emergence of the Internet of Things and the diffusion of wearable sensors. Although such devices may encourage people to pursue a healthier lifestyle, privacy concerns were raised in regards to the information that is collected. Most commercial smart watches and smartbands gather a wide variety of personal data from in-built sensors: number of steps, calories consumption, heart rate, and often even sleep duration. All these data are related to the fitness traits and habits of the user, and are known as *personal fitness information* (PFI). One of the main concerns regarding the disclosure of these data is related to the possibility of building a so-called “quantified self” that emerges from continuous collection of PFI by sensors constantly monitoring the user. Moreover, the entities that might gain access to users’ PFI are not limited to the manufacturer of the smartband: several fitness apps allow to share PFI data with contacts or to post them on social networks, and users are inclined to do so, as this provides additional motivation to stay active and exercise (Alqhatani and Lipford, 2019).

In this work, we explore an attack aimed at identifying one target user in an aggregated database by exploiting specific PFI records, namely, time series of steps and calories. More specifically, we investigate

a scenario where an adversary has already obtained other records of the target user from other sources (e.g., posts on social networks), as shown in Fig. 1. We distinguish between two main cases: in the first case, the attacker is certain that one of the time series in the database belongs to the target; in the second, the attacker is not sure whether the target is actually present in the database. Our approach consists in finding a time series in the database containing the highest amount of samples that are “similar” to those already owned by the adversary. The way we define similarity between samples is explained in the next Section 4. Our contributions can be summarized as:

- showing a method based on known machine learning algorithms that allows to link time series containing similar PFI records;
- measuring the probability for our method to find a user in a group of N users;
- using our results to demonstrate the identifying capability of PFI records.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the related work. In Section 3, we describe the problem more in details, and we introduce the notation used. The method that we use in our implementation of the linking attack is presented in Section 4. The datasets employed in our experiments are listed in Section 5. We present experimental results in Section 6. Possible directions for future work are considered in Section 7. Finally, section 8 concludes the paper.

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Figure 1: In our threat model, PFI records of the target user (Bob) are stored in a public database, aggregated with other records. The attacker (Eve) has access to some other PFI records from Bob (e.g., she extracts such information from Bob’s posts on social media) and uses them to link the aggregated records to Bob.

2 RELATED WORK

Personal fitness information collected by wearables has been object of several studies on security and privacy. Christovich (Christovich, 2016) discussed the solutions for protecting PFI data, and proposed statutory guidelines to handle them. Another point examined in this work was the possibility of employing PFI data to build a “quantified self”, i.e., an individual profile built from continuous tracking of a user. This concern was supported by a number of recent studies, which employed PFI data from smartbands to infer health-related information. Sathyanarayana et al. (Sathyanarayana et al., 2016) utilized daily activity data from wearables to predict the quality of user’s sleep. Al-Makhadmeh and Tolba (Al-Makhadmeh and Tolba, 2019) employed Boltzmann deep belief neural networks to predict heart diseases using features derived from heart rate and blood pressure records. Zhu et al. (Zhu et al., 2020) proposed a framework that leverages heart rate and sleep data to detect symptoms of COVID-19 with the purpose of predicting pandemic’s trends.

3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this work we explore two scenarios, both involving a smartband user (Bob) and an attacker (Eve) as actors. We assume that Eve possesses some PFI data y from Bob, which consist of a sequence of steps and calories collected on different days. Using these records, Eve aims at finding Bob in a public database, which contains fitness information on N smartband users $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N$. The information consists of time series of PFI records x_1, \dots, x_N , and of some additional data, e.g., users’ sleep information or diet. Eve tries to find Bob inside this database by verifying which time series among x_1, \dots, x_N has most “similar” samples to

y . This way, she can glean the additional information about Bob that is contained in the data.

The two scenarios that we investigate are the following:

Scenario 1 We assume that the presence of Bob in the database is certain and that Eve is aware of it. In this case, she needs to determine who is Bob among $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N$. A naive guess, i.e., choosing one sequence at random, would lead to a success probability of $1/N$.

Scenario 2 We assume that Bob may or may not be in the database and Eve is not informed of which is the case. Therefore, in this scenario she has two tasks, i.e. to determine which user among $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N$ is more likely to be Bob and to verify if he is actually Bob. So the possible conclusions that Eve can draw are that Bob is either $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N$, or none of them.

In both cases, Eve employs the data $y = (y^{(1)}, \dots, y^{(T)})$ in her possession and compares them with x_1, \dots, x_N to determine which is the most “similar”. In the second scenario, she also needs to determine if the most similar sequence is similar “enough” to conclude that the user is present in the database.

4 METHODS

In order to link the data of the target user y to his corresponding time series in the aggregated database, we employ an approach based on machine learning. The idea is that we train classification models on the samples from time series x_1, \dots, x_N and we use them to classify the samples from y . In particular, we consider each user in the database as a class and all samples from time series x_i belong to class θ_i . We use the number of samples that are assigned to the class θ_i as a measure of similarity between x_i and y . E.g., if most of the samples are labeled as θ_3 , we conclude that x_3 is the time series with most “similar” samples to y .

The training consists in defining a map from the feature space \mathcal{X} to the set of users $\Theta = \{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N\}$

$$\hat{f}: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \Theta, y^{(t)} \mapsto \hat{f}(y^{(t)}).$$

This map classifies single samples and assign them to the $\theta_i \in \Theta$ who is most likely to have produced them. We call \hat{f} *single-sample decision rule*, and we apply it on each of the records $y^{(1)}, \dots, y^{(T)}$ from the target user. Indeed, part of the samples – even a great part – may be classified incorrectly, and in general the samples of y will not be all assigned to the same class.

Therefore, we make the final prediction using a *majority rule*

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta_i \in \Theta} \left| \{y^{(t)} : \hat{f}(y^{(t)}) = \theta_i, t = 1, \dots, T'\} \right|. \quad (1)$$

That is, we use \hat{f} to classify independently each sample of y and we choose the class (user) $\hat{\theta}$ that has been selected most times. Notice that in order for the majority rule to work, \hat{f} is not even required to have a high accuracy. The only requirement is that \hat{f} must predict the correct user more frequently (i.e., with higher probability) than any other user. E.g., if when a sample is produced by θ_3 , the rule \hat{f} predicts θ_3 with 30% probability and any other user with less than 30% probability, then on average the majority rule will predict θ_3 correctly.

In our experiments, we tested the following algorithms to train the single-sample prediction rule: k -Nearest Neighbors (kNN) (Kuncheva and Jain, 1999), Random Forests (RF) (Ho, 1995), Support Vector Machines (SVM) (Hearst et al., 1998) with RBF kernel, and Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) (Parzen, 1962) with Gaussian kernel.

Determining the presence of the user in the database. In the second scenario that we study, it is not known whether the target is present in the aggregated database. For this case, we first link the target's data y to the closest user in the database, adopting the same decision rule from the first scenario. Then, we compute a score that estimates how confident we are about our choice. Given the target's sequence y and the sequence x_i produced by the selected user θ_i , a subscore $s(x_i, y^{(t)})$ is computed for each sample $y^{(t)}$ as

$$s(x_i, y^{(t)}) = \min_{\tau} \|x_i^{(\tau)} - y^{(t)}\| \quad (2)$$

that is the Euclidean distance between $y^{(t)}$ and the closest sample of x_i . The final score is obtained by averaging the subscores,

$$S(x_i, y) = \frac{100}{T'} \sum_{t=1}^{T'} s(x_i, y^{(t)}). \quad (3)$$

The factor 100 is used solely for rescaling. Intuitively this score measures the average distance between closest samples from x_i and y . Hence, the lower the score, the closest are the two sequences and the more likely it is that they have been produced by the same user. The final decision of whether θ_i is actually the target user is taken by comparing $S(x_i, y)$ to a threshold. If the score is above the threshold we conclude that the target is not present in the database, otherwise we conclude that he is θ_i .

5 DATASETS

In our experiments we employ two datasets, which we call dataset D1 and dataset D2, both containing daily PFI records from different users collected by Fitbit devices. We extract only information about daily number of steps and calories consumption from each user and ignore the remaining information. The first half of the samples is used to simulate the aggregated data on which the decision rule is trained. The second half, instead, is used for prediction to simulate the data collected by the adversary.

Dataset D1 The first dataset comprises 35 users recorded from March 2016 to May 2016, covering a total of 61 days.

The dataset is available at: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.53894>. However, in this dataset one user was present in the first month but not in the second, and hence was removed.

Dataset D2 The second dataset, called PMData (Thambawita et al., 2020), comprises 16 users recorded for a period of 5 months, from November 2019 to April 2019, covering a total of 151 days.

The dataset is available at: <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/k2apb>.

In both datasets, we discarded the samples that contained zeros and removed the users with too few non-zero samples. In the end, the first 29 users were kept for D1 and the first 9 were kept for D2.

6 EXPERIMENTS

In our experiments we estimate the success probability P_{succ} of a linking attack in scenario 1, where the target is certainly present in the aggregated database and the adversary is aware of it; and scenario 2, where the target is present in the database with probability p . We show how the results vary with the number of users in the database N and with the inclusion probability p . We repeated each of our experiments doing a Monte Carlo sampling for a number $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$ of iterations and averaged the results.

Choice of the hyperparameters. In our experiments, we opted for an arbitrary choice of the hyperparameters rather than fine-tuning them through some validation techniques. The reason is that our goal is not to build a fine-tuned model with highest performance, but only to show that a learned \hat{f} combined

Method	Hyperparameter	Value
kNN	number of neighbors k	1
RF	number of trees n	10
SVM	C	10^3
	γ	0.5
KDE	bandwidth h	0.5

Table 1: Hyperparameters employed for the machine learning methods.

with the majority rule allows to perform the linking attack with reasonable accuracy.

6.1 Scenario 1

In scenario 1, we estimate the probability of success of the linking attack for N users as the accuracy of our predictions. That is, we count the number n_{succ} of correct predictions and we divide it by the total number of predictions:

$$P_{\text{succ}} = \frac{n_{\text{succ}}}{n_{\text{tot}}}.$$

After initializing the counter of correct predictions at $n_{\text{succ}} = 0$, we repeat the following loop $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$ times:

1. Sample N users $\theta_{i_1}, \dots, \theta_{i_N}$ at random from the dataset.
2. Train the model on the training points x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_N} from the sampled users.
3. Choose one user uniformly at random among $\theta_{i_1}, \dots, \theta_{i_N}$ and make the prediction on his test points y .
4. If the prediction is correct, update the counter of correct predictions n_{succ} .

We compare our results with a naive approach which consists in guessing the user at random, with a success probability of $1/N$.

Results for varying number of users. The first experiment that we run consists in checking how P_{succ} scales for an increasing number of users N . In order to do so, we repeat the steps mentioned above, varying the value of N from 1 to the maximum number of available users. We employ the first half of the samples for training and the other half for testing.

The results are displayed in Figure 2. For dataset D1, all the methods obtained an accuracy above 60% even when the model is trained on all the 29 users. Moreover, kNN with $k = 1$ has the best performance, with a success probability above 78% on both datasets. For dataset D2, we obtained worse results when the number of users reached the maximum (i.e., 9), which can be possibly explained by the presence of two similar users. Since the overall number of

Figure 2: The success probability P_{succ} estimated for varying number N of users.

users is small, it is likely that if two similar users are present, they are sampled often.

6.2 Scenario 2

In scenario 2, depending on whether a user is actually included or not, the detection rule can lead to different outcomes¹:

- *true positive* (TP), if the target is included and the rule correctly identifies him;
- *false negative* (FN), if the target is included and the rule fails to detect him;
- *true negative* (TN), if the target is not included and the rule concludes that he is actually not present;
- *false positive* (FP), if the target is not included and the rule detects one user as the target.

Distinguishing between these outcomes allows us to estimate the probability of success, conditioned on

¹It is worth remarking that the definitions of true positive and false negative are different from the standard ones.

the user being or not in the database, respectively as

$$P_{\text{succ|in}} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \text{ and } P_{\text{succ|out}} = \frac{\text{TN}}{\text{TN} + \text{FP}}. \quad (4)$$

These two probabilities are known in literature as recall and specificity. In addition, using the law of total probability, it is possible to compute the success probability for a generic value of p as

$$P_{\text{succ|}p} = pP_{\text{succ|in}} + (1-p)P_{\text{succ|out}}. \quad (5)$$

When the user has the same probability of being included or not in the database (i.e., $p = 0.5$) $P_{\text{succ|}0.5}$ is known as balanced accuracy. The experiments are conducted following an analogous procedure to scenario 1, repeating the test for $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$ times and averaging the results. Indeed, in these experiments the user can be sampled either from $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N$ or from the other users available in the datasets. To identify the target, we employ the kNN method with $k = 1$, which provides the best results in scenario 1.

Results for varying threshold. We first evaluate how $P_{\text{succ|in}}$ and $P_{\text{succ|out}}$ change for different values of the threshold. The first plot of Figure 3 shows that the threshold allows to regulate a tradeoff between recall and specificity. In particular, when the threshold is low, most of the times the rule concludes that the user is not present in the database, so $P_{\text{succ|in}}$ is low, and $P_{\text{succ|out}}$ is high. Conversely, when the threshold increases, $P_{\text{succ|in}}$ grows and $P_{\text{succ|out}}$ decreases. Threshold 10 is the value giving almost equal importance to the positive and negative cases. Moreover, from equation 5 we can infer that the two probabilities constitute bounds for $P_{\text{succ|}p}$. This is shown graphically in the second plot of Figure 3. Since $P_{\text{succ|}p}$ is a convex combination of $P_{\text{succ|in}}$ and $P_{\text{succ|out}}$, the two probabilities constitute the extremes of the line at $p = 1$ and $p = 0$, respectively. We show only the plot for dataset D1, since dataset D2 provides analogous results.

Results for varying number of users. We fix the threshold value to 10 and we vary the number N of users in the database. We compare the performance of our method with two naive rules. The first one is *naive rejection*, which consists in always concluding that the user is not present in the database and has success probability $1 - p$. The second one is *naive guessing*, and consists in choosing with equal probability one of the users or “not present in the database”. The success probability of such rule is $1/(N + 1)$ regardless of the value of p (it can be easily verified by applying the law of total probability). Our method shows better performance of both the naive rules in most cases. Naive rejection appears to provide close

Figure 3: On the top, $P_{\text{succ|in}}$ and $P_{\text{succ|out}}$ of the score method in scenario 2, estimated for fixed number of users $N = 15$ and varying threshold. On the bottom, $P_{\text{succ|}p}$ for different values of inclusion probability p , $N = 15$ and threshold 10. Results are for dataset D1.

performance, but on the other hand it never allows to find the target user when he is actually present.

Figure 4 shows the behavior of balanced accuracy $P_{\text{succ|}0.5}$ for increasing number of users in both datasets. The success rate is lower compared to scenario 1, as expected since the task is more complex, but still between 50% and 70%.

7 FUTURE WORK

We foresee two main continuations for this work. The first consists in expanding the study of linking attacks on personal fitness information. One idea may be to vary the PFI features that are employed in the attack: e.g., it could be interesting to investigate how the success probability changes if sleep patterns or heartbeat records are included in the data. Furthermore, it will be necessary to make experiments on larger datasets, in order to confirm the validity of our results and to apply more refined techniques requiring more data.

A second possibility may be to study the effectiveness of anonymization techniques as countermeasures for linking attacks. Applying straightforwardly concepts like k -anonymity or differential privacy to time

Figure 4: Success probability of the score method in scenario 2, estimated for varying number N of users and fixed threshold 10. The probability of inclusion for the target is fixed at $p = 0.5$.

series data will most of the times cause an excessive loss of information, making the anonymized data unusable, so a main aspect to be addressed is the tradeoff between utility and privacy when protecting PFI data.

8 CONCLUSIONS

Throughout this paper, we investigated the problem of leveraging personal fitness information to find a target in a set of N people. Our results show that using just steps and calories it is possible to identify the user with higher probability compared to random guessing. We focused on a specific threat model where an attacker tries to find a target user in an aggregated dataset. However, identifiable data are prone to a wider pool of threats that need to be addressed. We hope that this will raise awareness on the sensitivity of personal fitness information, and that it will lay the foundation for future works aimed at protecting it.

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